

California Ridgway's Rail
(*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*)

5-Year Review:
Summary and Evaluation

Photo Credit: Robert Clark/National Science Foundation

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U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office

Sacramento, California

5-YEAR REVIEW

California Ridgeway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*)

GENERAL INFORMATION:

Subspecies: California Ridgeway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*)

Date listed: October 13, 1970

FR citation(s): 35 FR 16047

Classification: Endangered species

BACKGROUND:

Most recent status review:

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2020. Five-Year Review: California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Field Office. Sacramento, California. August 31, 2020. 33 pp.

FR notice citation announcing this status review:

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2024. (89 FR 83510); Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; initiation of 5-year status reviews for 59 Pacific southwest species; October 16, 2024.

ASSESSMENT:

California Ridgeway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) is a subspecies of Ridgeway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*; Chesser et al. 2014, 2024). Ridgeway's rail is a member of the rail family (*Rallidae*) that occurs in suitable habitat from the San Francisco Bay area of California to the Pacific coast of west-central México. Closely related species of *Rallus* and subspecies of *Rallus obsoletus* occur along the Gulf of México, throughout the Caribbean, and along coastal South America (Maley and Brumfield 2013). The use of "Ridgeway" in the common name is in honor of Robert Ridgeway, the American ornithologist.

Taxonomy:

In prior Service documents, including the most recent 5-year review (Service 2020a), California Ridgeway's rail has been called California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). Maley and Brumfield (2013) used genetic information and geographic analysis to re-evaluate the phylogenetic relationships among the species and subspecies in the clapper/king rail complex, which included California clapper rail. Maley and Brumfield recommended a taxonomic restructuring of the complex and proposed that the members of what they called the *R. longirostris obsoletus* group be renamed Ridgeway's rail, and given a new species name *R. obsoletus*. This new species included six subspecies from *R. longirostris*: *R. l. obsoletus*, *R. l. levipes*, *R. l. beldingi*, *R. l. yumanensis*, *R. l. rhizophorae*, and *R. l. nayaritensis*. Chesser et al. (2014) accepted Maley and Brumfield's proposed species name change to Ridgeway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), including the six subspecies. Wood et al. (2017) followed Chesser et al. (2014) using *R. o. obsoletus* and the common name California Ridgeway's rail. Eddleman and Conway (2018) discussed the status of the subspecies in the new Ridgeway's rail (*R. obsoletus*) species and maintained six subspecies including *R. o. obsoletus*. Eddleman and Conway did not list common

names for the *R. obsoletus* subspecies names. In 2023, the Service made changes to the endangered species list to reflect current scientifically accepted nomenclature for migratory birds and changed California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) to California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) (Service 2023a). Thus, in this 5-year review the Service uses the name California Ridgway's rail (*R. o. obsoletus*).

Population Status and Trends:

The number of California Ridgway's rail detected during annual surveys prior to the most recent 5-year review are described in Service (2020). Point Blue Conservation Science (PBCS 2022) coordinated range-wide surveys in 2019 through 2021 with the goal of estimating the range-wide population size of California Ridgway's rail. The details of this analysis are described in Point Blue (2022). This analysis concluded that the range-wide population of California Ridgway's rail in 2019-2021 was between 1,101 and 1,751 using a 90% confidence interval, with average population size of 1,426. This included an average estimate of 671 California Ridgway's rails in San Pablo Bay, 703 rails in San Francisco Bay, and 52 rails in central San Francisco Bay. A reproducible and comprehensive analysis of population trends over recent years has not yet been completed.

Information acquired since the last status review:

Point Blue Conservation Science completed annual California Ridgway's rail surveys at selected high priority locations and marshes from 2020 through 2025 (PBCS 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025). The reports associated with these annual surveys included conclusions and recommendations for present and future recovery activities. These conclusions and recommendations include: marshes that are larger and have a lower perimeter to area ratio tend to support higher densities of rails; rail densities tend to respond positively to tidal marsh restoration efforts; higher channel densities tend to support higher rail densities; and rails tend to do best when there is a mixture of low, medium and high elevation habitat in occupied marshes.

The Invasive *Spartina* Project (ISP) completed annual surveys for California Ridgway's rails in the San Francisco estuary from 2020 through 2025 (OEI 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024). These annual reports describe rail detections by marsh and region and consider trends in numbers of detections across recent years, with a focus on how treatments for invasive and hybrid *Spartina* and re-establishment of native *Spartina* may be influencing rail populations in marsh habitat across the survey area. The ISP surveys documented the following numbers of California Ridgway's rail detections over this period: 798 detections during surveys of 100 sub-areas in 2020; 556 detections during surveys of 94 sub-areas in 2021; 499 detections during surveys of 95 sub-areas in 2022; 516 detections during surveys of 95 sub-areas in 2023; and 519 detections during surveys at 100 sub-areas in 2024. The 2025 survey has been conducted, but the data have not yet been reported. Rohmer and Kerr (2023) describe the most recent data related to invasive *Spartina* monitoring and treatment.

California Department of Fish and Wildlife conducted annual secretive marsh bird surveys in Suisun Marsh with a focus on California Ridgway's rail and California black rail (CDFW 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024). These surveys did not document California Ridgway's rail. These reports concluded that Suisun marsh may not currently represent preferred habitat for California

Ridgway's rail, but that this area may become increasingly important if anthropogenic impacts make other marsh complexes less suitable habitat.

The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service conducted annual secretive marsh surveys at Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge and San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge (Service 2020b, 2021, 2022a, 2022b, 2023b, 2023c, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2025), with a focus on California Ridgway's rails. These reports include discussion of the history of rail monitoring on the Refuges, survey methodology, ongoing predator control, ongoing invasive plant control including discussion of the ISP, and ongoing tidal marsh restoration projects. The Service continues annual secretive marsh surveys and invasive *Spartina* surveys at both Refuges and continues invasive broad-leaved pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*) monitoring every three years at San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge (Service 2019).

U.S. Geological Survey completed a California Ridgway's rail translocation and radiotracking study (Overton and Casazza 2022). The study sites for this project included three marshes (Arrowhead, Laumeister, McGinnis) in the San Francisco and San Pablo bays. Twenty-eight rails were radiotracked and monitored during the study, resulting in almost 31,000 location estimates for the rails. This study resulted in fine-scale temporal and geospatial information on female and male rails divided into treatment (translocation) and control (resident) groups, as well as survival data for treatment and control rails.

RECOVERY CRITERIA:

Service (2013) articulated downlisting and delisting criteria for California Ridgway's rail. These downlisting criteria are described in detail in Service 2013 and include: protection and management of habitat at each of the marsh complexes sufficient to support target California Ridgway's rail population sizes; reduction of invasive broad-leaved pepperweed within marsh complexes; the development and implementation of an early detection and response program for invasive plants that have the potential to impact California Ridgway's rail populations; implementation of site-specific management plans on lands owned by the Service, California Department of Fish and Game, East Bay Regional Park District, and the Mid-Peninsula Open Space District; development and implementation of predator management plans for all marsh complexes with significant predator issues; maintenance of California Ridgway's rail populations in each recovery unit to provide resiliency to stochastic events; and the preservation or creation of high marsh and/or upland transitions lands as part of new marsh restoration efforts, along with management of these areas as needed to allow for the landward migration of California Ridgway's rail in response to sea level raise. California Ridgway's rail downlisting criteria (Service 2013) and the most recent status analysis of (Wood et al. 2022) for number of rails detected and available habitat in each recovery unit and marsh complex are shown in Table 1. While the current estimated number of acres of available rail habitat has been met in some of the segments of the Central/Southern San Francisco Bay recovery unit, the number of rails in these segments is substantially lower than would be expected if downlisting criteria had been met.

CONCLUSIONS:

A core consideration in this decision in evaluating downlisting or delisting was the current resiliency, redundancy, and representation of the subspecies (Smith et al. 2018). Resiliency is considered to be the ability of California Ridgway's rail to continue to maintain viable populations when exposed to environmental and demographic stochasticity, such as associated with typical variation in climate and weather conditions in tidal marsh habitat in the San Francisco Bay region, and in the reproductive and survival rates of the rails in the various populations. Redundancy is the ability of California Ridgway's rail to withstand catastrophic events that have the potential to cause the extinction of one or more populations of rails, but that would not be expected to cause the extinction of the subspecies, so long as there are multiple populations distributed in geographic space with suitable distance among populations. Representation is the ability of California Ridgway's rail to adapt to changes in environmental conditions that might plausibly occur in tidal marsh habitat across the range of this rail. The Service assumed that genetic diversity and/or diversity among populations that are physiologically or behaviorally adapted to a variety of environmental conditions would improve the viability of the subspecies. In developing recovery criteria for California Ridgway's rail, Service (2013) established downlisting and delisting criteria that would promote relatively high resilience, redundancy, and representation for this subspecies.

After reviewing the best available scientific information, we conclude that California Ridgway's rail remains an endangered species. The evaluation of threats affecting the species under the factors in 4(a)(1) of the Endangered Species Act and analysis of the status of the species in our 2020 status review remains an accurate reflection of the current status of California Ridgway's rail.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS:

Proposed work related to California Ridgway's rail could include: continuing annual California Ridgway's rail surveys until the next 5-year review; conducting at least one range-wide population analysis similar to Wood et al. (2022) before the next 5-year review; and developing a statistical approach for evaluating the populations trends of California Ridgway's rail within the various marsh complexes in its range.

FIELD OFFICE APPROVAL:

Donald (Donnie) Ratcliff, Field Supervisor
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service

Recovery Unit	Segment Name	Segment Code	Target CRR Habitat	Current Estimated CRR	Target Acres	Current Estimated Acres
CSSF	San Rafael Creek-Richardson Bay	I	180	27	400	433
CSSF	Bair-Greco-Ravenswood	N	500	164	1,111	2,945
CSSF	East Palo Alto-Guadalupe Slough	O	500	82	1,111	1,582
CSSF	Guadalupe Slough-Warm Springs	P	500	35	1,111	1,388
CSSF	Mowry-Dumbarton	Q	500	80	1,111	1,278
CSSF	Hwy 84 to Hwy 92	R & S	500	39	1,111	1,467
CSSF	Hwy 92-Arrowhead Marsh	K & T	500	60	1,111	813
CSSF	Recovery Unit Total	--	3,180	487	7,066	9,906
SPB	China Camp to Petaluma River	G	500	94	2,500	958
SPB	Petaluma River marshes	F	500	104	2,500	2,368
SPB	Petaluma River to Sonoma Creek	E	500	51	2,500	952
SPB	Napa Marshes	D	500	10	2,500	1,263
SPB	Point Pinole marsh	H	80	48	400	508
SPB	Recovery Unit Subtotal	--	1,580	307	7,900	2,723
SBA	Suisun Bay area		100	0	5,000	NE
CC	Tomaes Bay		--	0	800	NE

Note: This table shows the downlisting criteria in the tidal marsh recovery plan (Service 2013) for habitat to support given numbers of rails for each area (Target CRR Habitat) along with most recent rail estimates (Current Estimated CRR), and the target number of acres for rails (Target Acres) along with current estimated acres (Current Estimated Acres). Abbreviations: CSSFB = Central/Southern San Francisco Bay recovery unit, SPB = San Pablo Bay recovery unit, SBA = Suisun Bay area, CC = Central Coast recovery unit, Hwy = highway, NE = not estimated.

Table 1: California Ridgway’s rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) downlisting criteria and status as of 2021 for number of rails and available habitat in each recovery unit and marsh complex.

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